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PRESILIENT

Post-pandemic resilient communities: is the informal economy a reservoir for the next generation of digitalized and green businesses in the Global South?

Comparative Horizon Scanning Report

Informality and innovation: building post-pandemic resilient communities in **Senegal**.

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Executive Summary

This report is the result of a Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise conducted within the PRESILIENT project with the aim of investigating the role of the informal economy in building post-pandemic resilience in the Global South. The HS activity aimed to identify economic sectors most affected by the COVID-19 crisis, as well as those showing signs of adaptation, innovation, and recovery, with a particular focus on informal economic dynamics.

This Senegal-focused report employs qualitative and desk-based methods, including literature reviews, grey literature analysis, and media monitoring, to explore emerging socio-economic and political-economic trends within the country's informal economy. Unlike other country reports that often rely on large-scale quantitative data or automated keyword mapping, this contribution provides an in-depth interpretive analysis grounded in socio-economic perspectives and political economy scholarship. The report draws specifically on research from the field of socio-economics, which views economic practices as intrinsically linked to the social, cultural, symbolic, and political contexts in which they occur. Indeed, while the informal economy is firmly situated within the economic domain, it also plays a critical role in processes of social reproduction and cohesion, encompassing distinct modes of sociability, networks, and value systems – dimensions that lie clearly beyond the purview of mainstream economics.

Key findings indicate that while service-oriented informal sectors – such as tourism, hospitality, transport, and street vending – were severely affected, small-scale agriculture and certain digital services showed relative resilience. The pandemic disproportionately impacted women, both through the prolonged closure of women-led businesses and increased unpaid care responsibilities. Structural inequalities were further exacerbated by dynamics such as the persistent competition between small-scale producers and industrial actors, contributing to increasing precarity among the former. Despite these challenges, grassroots responses – including women's solidarity networks – played a vital role in sustaining communities and advancing economic adaptation. These findings call for policy approaches that address inequality at its root and support locally grounded, community-driven economies.

Keywords

Senegal / Senegalese; Globalization / Globalisation; Debt; Privatization; Trade; COVID-19 / Covid19 / pandemic; Inflation; Employment / Work / Labor / Labour; Informality; Precarity; Entrepreneurship; Survival Economy; Business / Businesses; Inequality / Inequalities; Poverty; Local Communities; Social Movements; Political Tensions; Women.

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Introduction

This document is part of the PRESILIENT project's WP1 deliverables and presents the Senegalese country-level contribution to the Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise. The Horizon Scanning methodology, as defined in the PRESILIENT Global Research Protocol, is a collective and comparative tool used to identify early signals, opportunities, and risks that may shape the future of informal economies in the Global South. The overarching aim is to trace which sectors declined or expanded in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic and to identify those that could contribute to resilient and inclusive post-pandemic recovery pathways.

The HS exercise across PRESILIENT's 15-country network was designed to be flexible and adapted to the specificity of each context. While the general methodological protocol outlined the use of mixed methods and potential integration of bibliometric and quantitative trend analyses, each Early-Stage Researcher (ESR) was also encouraged to adapt the tools according to their disciplinary background and access to sources. In this case, the report adopts a qualitative approach, focusing on sectoral fluctuations and emerging inequalities driven by structural pressures, as well as on the creative adaptations of local actors to these dynamics. Fully aware of the limitations of certain statistical classifications and categories, the report nonetheless integrates quantitative data that can help capture the scale of phenomena at a more macro level.

In this Senegalese case, the methodological approach specifically focused on:

- A thematic review of the academic literature, reports related to informality, socio-economic livelihoods, and resilience in the aftermath of the pandemic in Senegal.
- An analysis of grey literature, reports, and policy documents.
- A comparative reading of media narratives, which sought to differentiate media sources beyond the mainstream, despite the limitation of not including sources in Wolof.
- An engagement with political economy and critical development studies addressing locally grounded and community-based economies. This approach is consistent with PRESILIENT's epistemological stance, which does not reduce informality to a statistical anomaly to be corrected, but instead recognizes it as an intrinsic part of the economic system, as well as a field of knowledge and potential innovation.

In this context, the findings contribute to a comparative understanding of post-pandemic dynamics and will inform the subsequent phases of the project, including expert-based Delphi surveys and case study development. They also offer policy-relevant insights by challenging dominant assumptions about formalization and proposing inclusive transformations for the economy.

Methodological Note on Data Collection and Processing

This report follows the common research protocol defined by the PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning (HS) framework. While qualitative and interpretive in orientation, the exercise also followed a structured approach to ensure cross-country comparability. The data collection process was based on the identification and use of pre-defined keywords related to informality, economic recovery, and resilience. In line with the shared methodological guidelines, the research drew on 150 sources, comprising 50 academic references, 50 grey literature or policy documents, and 50 media articles. Academic references were identified through targeted searches on Google Scholar in both English and French, filtered from 2020 onward. Grey literature was gathered via similar searches on Google Scholar, Google, and selected organizational websites, also limited to post-2020 materials. Media articles were sourced exclusively through Google searches, using the same time filter. All sources were curated for relevance, closely read, coded, and interpreted in light of the researcher's contextual knowledge.

Although this Senegalese case study prioritizes qualitative synthesis, it remains grounded in a systematic data-gathering process consistent across the PRESILIENT network, further valuing the use of quantitative data for understanding economic phenomena. As such, the report contributes a robust and contextually informed analysis that aligns with the project's collective goals and epistemological commitments.

Informal Economies in Senegal: Socioeconomic Context

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The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic led to a time of significant disruption in Senegal, worsening pre-existing vulnerabilities and bringing in new challenges. The pandemic severely affected employment opportunities. It further had unequal gender impacts, with women-led informal firms more likely to stay closed temporarily and for longer periods than male-led firms. Women – more than men – also experienced an increase in the intensity of unpaid domestic and care work.

The sectors most affected by the pandemic in Senegal were tourism, hospitality services, and transport. Informal small-scale service and trading activities were particularly hard hit, facing income loss, reduced market access, and heightened vulnerability. Restrictions severely disrupted street vending, forcing many vendors to deplete their savings or incur debt to survive. Other informal sectors deeply affected by the crisis included hairdressing, tailoring, catering, and the broader events industry. Physical distancing measures and limits on public gatherings brought family and social ceremonies to a halt, cutting off a key source of income for those working in these informal activities. Small informal businesses within the food supply chain also faced distress and insolvency due to logistical disruptions. While restrictive measures created marketing challenges across agri-food sectors, the closure of fishing docks particularly impacted female processors and small-scale fish sellers. More broadly, the fishing industry experienced significant setbacks under lockdown. However, the artisanal fishing sector had already been severely affected prior to the pandemic by overfishing linked to industrial bottom trawling for foreign markets.

Among the more resilient sectors, e-payment companies and e-commerce platforms adapted quickly and even benefited during this period. Agriculture also showed relative resilience, marked by a growing shift toward agroecological practices, particularly among rural women, despite logistical and marketing challenges. While several value chains – such as onions, mangoes, and poultry – were heavily impacted, others like cashew nuts managed to adapt and recover quickly. The mining sector experienced overall growth, with revenues from industrial mining rising due to strong gold production and favorable global prices, although artisanal mining was suspended for much of 2020.

Regional and Global Comparison

In the Senegalese context, tourism was a major theme in national media, contrasts with global patterns where it appears more in research publications; its visibility in Senegal reflects both its economic significance and vulnerability. Transportation, though less emphasized in global comparisons, stands out in Senegal due to the government-imposed ban on intercity travel, which had wide-ranging impacts and is highlighted in both the national data and the report's introduction as one of the hardest-hit sectors.

Agriculture and food supply also held a central place in the Senegalese data, consistent with global trends showing the sector's overall resilience. However, intra-sectoral disparities – especially in specific crops and fishing – and disruptions in food trade and sales exposed vulnerabilities in this key area of the informal economy. The fact that this sector is particularly present in the data collected on Senegal is easily explained by its importance in the national economy, and in the informal economy especially. This is also an issue of major political debate and one that many Senegalese organizations are working on. Other sectors received heightened attention in Senegal compared to the global data, such as waste management, due to local concerns around the Mbeubeuss dumpsite, and missing sectors like hairdressing, tailoring, and catering for family and social ceremonies, which are crucial to Senegal's informal labor market but overlooked in the comparative report. The sector of extractive industries is also specific to the Senegalese context.

Emerging Trends and Feedback

Emerging trends in Senegal's socio-economic and political economy landscape reveal both significant challenges and potential opportunities.

High levels of public debt raise concerns about the government's long-term socio-economic sovereignty. In the digital economy, while national efforts to promote e-commerce and digitalization offer hope for growth, scholars stress the importance of locally grounded projects supported by accessible and context-appropriate technologies (Sylla, 2023). In tourism-related activities, nature-based solutions are often advanced for their conservation value and their potential to support post-Covid economic recovery.

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However, research also points to dynamics of land appropriation and socio-economic inequality linked to tourism-oriented protected areas. In Niombato, for example, customary land rights have been weakened, and nature-based tourism businesses – often owned by white European men and employing local African workers – mirror enduring neo-colonial, patriarchal, and racial structures (Hiraldo & Böhm, 2023). Similar tensions emerge in the agri-food and fisheries sectors, where growing competition from industrial actors risks deepening territorial inequalities and sidelining small-scale producers and family farming, particularly in the context of export-driven fish production and resulting local shortages (FAO et al., 2022; Dème et al., 2020, 2023).

Against this backdrop, social and solidarity economics have offered alternative pathways for resilience and adaptation. Participative cooperatives such as BOOK DIOM, created by waste recyclers, exemplify the role of collective organization during the crisis (WIEGO, 2021). Women's groups, in particular, were central in mobilizing resources and supporting communities through food distribution, counseling, and the equitable management of aid, building on a long history of engagement for women's rights and improved economic conditions.

Related Outputs and Publications

This national report is part of the broader Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise developed within the PRESILIENT project. The following outputs have been produced from this collective research:

- Molina, J. L., Pulgar Corrotea, M., Polese, A., Fradejas-García, I., Ianole-Călin, R., Isaev, A., Mengato, S., Nguyen, M., Carracedo, D., De Lombaerde, G., Avesani, M., Sasikornwong, N., Gambardella, M., Andrias, B., Massera, M., Lima, J. P., Cisagara, B., Rahman, A., Kabaghe, W., & D'Urso, D. (2024). PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning Dataset [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14285318>

This dataset is the consolidated output of the Horizon Scanning research conducted across 15 countries in Africa, Asia, and Latin America (including Mexico). It comprises three corpora of references: academic literature, media articles, and grey literature sources, gathered and curated to explore economic transformations during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, with a focus on informal economies.

- Fradejas García, I., Pulgar, M., Molina, J. L., Ianole-Călin, R., & Polese, A. (2024). Volatility, growth, decline and sustainability perspective of domestic economic sectors after the pandemic: A comparative Horizon Scanning of 15 countries in Africa, Asia and Latin America. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14273561>

This comparative publication presents the aggregate results of the Horizon Scanning exercise conducted in 15 countries. Using a keyword-based supervised topic detection method across the combined corpora, it provides an overview of post-pandemic trends, highlighting convergences and divergences among countries and across types of sources. It also discusses patterns of economic volatility, recovery, and the sustainability of growth trajectories in the informal sector.

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